

USE OF DIAGNOSTIC TESTS IN FOREIGN SCHOOLS

Norqobilova Rayxona Davlatovna

Teacher of Termiz State Pedagogical Institute

Abstract: *this article provides information on the three stages of implementation in American school practice, the introduction and improvement of tests in schools in developed countries.*

Key words: *diagnosis, memory, attention, perception, letters, numbers, words, formulas, test, weight coefficient.*

The use of diagnostic tests in foreign schools has a long history. E. Thorndike (1874-1949), a recognized authority in the field of pedagogical testing, defines three stages of introducing the test into American school practice:

1. Search period (1900-1915). At this stage, there was an understanding and initial implementation of the tests of memory, attention, perception, etc., proposed by the French psychologist A. Bimet. Intelligence tests are being developed and tested to determine aptitude.

2. The next 15 years are the years of "noisy" in the development of school tests, which led to the final understanding of its role and place, possibilities and limitations. O. Stone's arithmetic, B. Zekingham's spelling test, E. Thorndike's diagnostic tests for most school subjects were developed and implemented. T. Kelly developed a method of measuring students' interests and inclinations (in learning algebra), and C. Spearman proposed general principles of using correlation analysis to standardize tests.

3. From 1931, the modern stage of the development of school tests begins. The search for experts is aimed at increasing the objectivity of tests, creating a continuous (end-to-end) system of school test diagnostics, adhering to a unified idea

and general principles, creating new, advanced means of providing and processing tests.

In this regard, let's remember that pedology developed in Russia at the beginning of the century implicitly accepted the test basis of objective school control.

After the decision of the Central Committee of the All-Union Bolshevik Communist Party "On Pedological Disorders in the System of People's Commissariat of Education" (1936), not only intellectual, but also harmless performance tests were eliminated. Attempts to restore them in the 70s did not lead to anything. In this regard, our science and practice is far behind that of foreign countries.

The introduction and improvement of tests in schools in developed countries continued at a rapid pace. Diagnostic tests of school performance are common, they include choosing the correct answer alternative from several reliable answers, writing a very short answer (filling in the blanks), adding letters, numbers, words, parts of formulas and others. With the help of these simple tasks, it is possible to collect important statistical material, mathematically process it, and obtain objective conclusions within the tasks provided for tests. Tests are printed in the form of sets, attached to textbooks, distributed on computer diskettes.

The problem of the ratio of oral and written forms of control is often resolved in favor of the latter. It is believed that verbal control is more helpful in developing quick response to questions, develops coherent speech, but does not provide proper objectivity. A written examination that provides high objectivity, in addition, helps to develop logical thinking, purposefulness: a student with a written control concentrates, studies the essence of the problem, thinks about solutions and composes an answer. Written control accustoms to the accuracy, brevity, and consistency of expressing thoughts.

In the field of setting assessment system(s), there is great diversity both in principles and in specific approaches, in the choice of assessment and assessment methods. Foreign schools use different systems for evaluating knowledge, skills and abilities, different rating scales are adopted, including one hundred, twelve, ten, two points, etc. In a French lycée, for example, when taking graduation exams. , the results are determined in a 20-point system. At the same time, a certain weight coefficient is determined for each subject, which determines the importance of this subject for the specialty, profile or department of the lyceum chosen by the student. With this, marks in core subjects will be given more weightage.

Due to the considerable decentralization of many foreign school systems, the curriculum and programs are subject to free choice of subjects by schools and students, and centralized testing and assessment of knowledge and skills are rarely implemented. For example, in Great Britain, the function of practical control over the quality of academic personnel training is assumed by the university commissions, to which all grammar and privileged schools are attached during the final examinations aimed at preparing their graduates. for additional university education.

In general, it should be recognized that monitoring and recording progress, diagnosing studies in foreign schools has the characteristics of an objective statement of results. This does not mean caring about universal education. The generally recognized principle of individualization of education requires one approach - everyone goes on his own path and pace, learns his abilities, needs, real values for the future.

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